

Direct measurements of V_{tb} and constraints on the Wtb anomalous couplings

Nello Bruscano - University of Pittsburgh
on behalf of the ATLAS & CMS collaborations

CKM 2018

10TH INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON THE CKM UNITARITY TRIANGLE
SEPTEMBER 17 – 21, 2018 | UNIVERSITÄT HEIDELBERG

Wtb vertex

At hadron colliders, top quarks predominantly produced

- * in pairs ($t\bar{t}$) via the flavour-conserving strong interaction ($g\bar{t}t$)
- * singly through the electroweak (EW) interaction (Wtb)

In $t\bar{t}$ production, Wtb vertex probed through top-quark decay

- * top quarks produced unpolarised and decayed through EW interaction ($t \rightarrow Wb$)

In single top-quark production, Wtb vertex studied in production and decay

- * production modes also sensitive to new physics

New effects above EWSB scale on Wtb vertex probed in a EFT approach

- * the most general Wtb lagrangian, including dim-6 operators

SM V-A term

$$\mathcal{L}_{Wtb} = -\frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} \bar{b} \gamma^\mu (V_L P_L + V_R P_R) t W_\mu^-$$
$$- \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} \bar{b} \frac{i\sigma^{\mu\nu} q_\nu}{M_W} (g_L P_L + g_R P_R) t W_\mu^- + \text{H.c.}$$

anom. coupl.

- * in SM, at tree level, $V_L = f_{LV} V_{tb}$, $f_{LV} = 1$, $V_R = g_L = g_R = 0$
 - ◇ CKM matrix element $V_{tb} \approx 1$
 - ◇ f_{LV} being a model-independent left-handed real form factor, encapsulating non-SM contributions
- * V_R , g_L and $g_R :=$ complex anomalous couplings
 - ◇ imaginary parts related with CP violation!

How to probe Wtb ?

Left-handed (LH) vector coupling V_L measured from

- * (directly) single top-quark production cross-section measurements
 - ◇ **assumption:** SM Wtb vertex ($V_R = g_L = g_R = 0$)
- * (indirectly) BR measurements in $t\bar{t}$ production (rather model dependent)

$$|V_L| := |f_{LV} V_{tb}| = \sqrt{\sigma/\sigma_{th}}$$

Assumptions: $V_R = g_L = g_R = 0$

$$|V_{td}|, |V_{ts}| \ll |V_{tb}|$$

Phys. Rev. D, 97, 013007 (2017)

How to probe Wtb ?

Anomalous couplings probed by means of top-quark related properties

- * W boson helicity fractions (F_0, F_L, F_R) in top-quark decays
- * single top-quark production and decay observables (angular distributions, etc)
 - ◇ different model assumptions according to the sensitive observable

$$F_i = N_i / (N_0 + N_L + N_R)$$

$i = 0, L, R$ (W polarizations)

Some assumptions needed:

2 ind. F , 4 (real) couplings

Phys. Rev. D, 97, 013007 (2017)

How to probe Wtb ?

Anomalous couplings probed by means of top-quark related properties

- * W boson helicity fractions (F_0, F_L, F_R) in top-quark decays
- * single top-quark production and decay observables (angular distributions, etc)
 - ◇ different model assumptions according to the sensitive observable

$$A_{FB}^i = (N_+ - N_-) / (N_+ + N_-),$$

$i = l, T, N$ (sensitive directions)

Assumption:

correlation neglected

Phys. Rev. D, 97, 013007 (2017)

How to probe Wtb ?

Anomalous couplings probed by means of top-quark related properties

- * W boson helicity fractions (F_0, F_L, F_R) in top-quark decays
- * single top-quark production and decay observables (angular distributions, etc)
 - ◇ different model assumptions according to the sensitive observable

3-differential decay,

$f_l, f_l^+, f_0^+, \delta_+, \delta_-, P$

No assumption

Phys. Rev. D, 97, 013007 (2017)

Direct constraints on V_L

ATLAS+CMS Preliminary
LHCtopWG

$$|f_{LV}V_{tb}| = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{\text{meas}}}{\sigma_{\text{theo}}}} \text{ from single top quark production} \quad \text{May 2018}$$

σ_{theo} : NLO+NNLL MSTW2008nnlo
PRD 83 (2011) 091503, PRD 82 (2010) 054018,
PRD 81 (2010) 054028

$\Delta\sigma_{\text{theo}}$: scale \oplus PDF

$m_{\text{top}} = 172.5 \text{ GeV}$

$|f_{LV}V_{tb}| \pm (\text{meas}) \pm (\text{theo})$

t-channel:

ATLAS 7 TeV¹
PRD 90 (2014) 112006 (4.59 fb⁻¹)

ATLAS 8 TeV^{1,2}
EPJC 77 (2017) 531 (20.2 fb⁻¹)

CMS 7 TeV
JHEP 12 (2012) 035 (1.17 - 1.56 fb⁻¹)

CMS 8 TeV
JHEP 06 (2014) 090 (19.7 fb⁻¹)

CMS combination 7+8 TeV
JHEP 06 (2014) 090

CMS 13 TeV²
PLB 772 (2017) 752 (2.3 fb⁻¹)

ATLAS 13 TeV²
JHEP 04 (2017) 086 (3.2 fb⁻¹)

Wt:

ATLAS 7 TeV
PLB 716 (2012) 142 (2.05 fb⁻¹)

CMS 7 TeV
PRL 110 (2013) 022003 (4.9 fb⁻¹)

ATLAS 8 TeV^{1,3}
JHEP 01 (2016) 064 (20.3 fb⁻¹)

CMS 8 TeV¹
PRL 112 (2014) 231802 (12.2 fb⁻¹)

LHC combination 8 TeV^{1,3} LHCtopWG
ATLAS-CONF-2016-023,
CMS-PAS-TOP-15-019

ATLAS 13 TeV²
EPJC 78 (2018) 186 (3.2 fb⁻¹)

s-channel:

ATLAS 8 TeV³
PLB 756 (2016) 228 (20.3 fb⁻¹)

¹ including top-quark mass uncertainty
² σ_{theo} : NLO PDF4LHC11
³ NPPS205 (2010) 10, CPC191 (2015) 74 including beam energy uncertainty

Latest results from ATLAS and CMS

- * CMS t-chan analysis at 13 TeV (35.9 fb⁻¹)
 - ◇ [TOP-17-011](#)
 - ◇ $|f_{LV}V_{tb}| = 1.00 \pm 0.05 (\text{meas}) \pm 0.02 (\text{theo})$
- * CMS tW analysis at 13 TeV
 - ◇ [CERN-EP-2018-074](#) (submitted to JHEP)
 - ◇ $\mu = 0.88 \pm 0.02(\text{stat}) \pm 0.09(\text{syst}) \pm 0.03(\text{lumi})$
- * ATLAS tW analysis at 13 TeV
 - ◇ [EPJC 78 \(2018\) 186](#)
 - ◇ $|f_{LV}V_{tb}| = 1.14 \pm 0.24 (\text{meas}) \pm 0.04 (\text{theo})$

Best combination at 7+8 TeV (CMS)

- * $|f_{LV}V_{tb}| = 0.998 \pm 0.041$
- * ATLAS+CMS Run I combination ongoing

W helicity fractions

Wtb properties in $t\bar{t}$ events determined by structure of weak interaction

* Helicity fractions (F_R, F_L, F_0) are determined by the Wtb vertex structure

$$\diamond F_0 + F_L + F_R = 1$$

Longitudinal W L-handed W R-handed W

$$F_L = 0.311 \pm 0.005$$

$$\rightarrow F_0 = 0.687 \pm 0.005$$

$$F_R = 0.0017 \pm 0.0001$$

The differential decay rate of top quarks considering the angle θ^* is given by:

$$\frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{d\sigma}{d \cos \theta^*} = \frac{3}{4} (1 - \cos^2 \theta^*) F_0 + \frac{3}{8} (1 - \cos \theta^*)^2 F_L + \frac{3}{8} (1 + \cos \theta^*)^2 F_R$$

* F_i depend on (real) anomalous couplings \Rightarrow deviations as hint of BSM physics

W helicity fractions

PLB 762 (2016) 512–534

Measurement in $t\bar{t}$ topology (19.8 fb⁻¹, 8 TeV)

- * cut-based analysis, e and μ channels
- * kinematic fitting to reconstruct $t\bar{t}$ system
 - ◇ leptonic side ONLY

Reweighting method:

- * top events $N_{t\bar{t}}$ reweighted according to decay function

$$w_{\text{lep/had/single-}t(\cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*; \vec{F})} \equiv \left[\frac{3}{8} F_L (1 - \cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*)^2 + \frac{3}{4} F_0 \sin^2\theta_{\text{gen}}^* + \frac{3}{8} F_R (1 + \cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*)^2 \right] / \left[\frac{3}{8} F_L^{\text{SM}} (1 - \cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*)^2 + \frac{3}{4} F_0^{\text{SM}} \sin^2\theta_{\text{gen}}^* + \frac{3}{8} F_R^{\text{SM}} (1 + \cos\theta_{\text{gen}}^*)^2 \right]$$

- * maximise a binned Poisson likelihood function

$$\mathcal{L}(\vec{F}) = \prod_i \frac{N_{\text{MC}}(i; \vec{F})^{N_{\text{data}}(i)}}{[N_{\text{data}}(i)]!} \exp[-N_{\text{MC}}(i; \vec{F})]$$

W helicity fractions

[Eur. Phys. J. C 77 \(2017\) 264](#)

ATLAS
EXPERIMENT

Measurement in $t\bar{t}$ topology (20.2 fb⁻¹, 8 TeV)

- * cut-based analysis
- * kinematic fitting to reconstruct $t\bar{t}$ system
 - ◇ leptonic and hadronic sides
 - ◇ hadronic analyser less sensitive

Template fit method:

- * templates for F_0, F_L, F_R (per-lepton channel) by reweighting reco. distribution

Very precise measurement!

Leptonic analyser (≥ 2 b-tags)

$$F_0 = 0.709 \pm 0.012 \text{ (stat.+bkg. norm.) } {}^{+0.015}_{-0.014} \text{ (syst.)}$$

$$F_L = 0.299 \pm 0.008 \text{ (stat.+bkg. norm.) } {}^{+0.013}_{-0.012} \text{ (syst.)}$$

$$F_R = -0.008 \pm 0.006 \text{ (stat.+bkg. norm.) } \pm 0.012 \text{ (syst.)}$$

- * combined likelihood fit (8 inputs) to extract helicity fractions

W helicity fractions

[Eur. Phys. J. C 77 \(2017\) 264](#)

ATLAS
EXPERIMENT

Possibility to set limits on anomalous Wtb couplings with EFTFitter tool

- * **limitation:** only place limits on combinations of (real) coupling pairs
 - ◇ other couplings set to their SM values \Rightarrow loss of generality

Allowed ranges:

- * $\text{Re}[V_R] \in [-0.24, 0.31] @ 95\% \text{ C.L.}$
- * $\text{Re}[g_L] \in [-0.14, 0.11] @ 95\% \text{ C.L.}$
- * $\text{Re}[g_R] \in [-0.02, 0.06] \text{ and } [0.74, 0.78] @ 95\% \text{ C.L.}$

*excluded by t-channel
x-sec*

Wtb couplings in t-channel

JHEP 02 (2017) 028

Search for anomalous Wtb couplings in t-channel single top quark production (24.7 fb⁻¹, 7-8 TeV)

- * one muon and two or three jets
- * Bayesian Neural Network (BNN) technique to separate V_L vs. V_R, g_R and g_L

* 1-2-3D constraints on the anomalous parameters are obtained

Agreement with SM predictions

Global constraints

[Phys. Rev. D, 97, 013007 \(2017\)](#)

Combining x-sec, W-helicity and asymmetry to increase sensitivity to BSM

- * in the EFT framework
- * most recent asymmetries result from ATLAS included
- * very general approach: couplings (real+imaginary) allowed to vary simultaneously

Global constraints

[Phys. Rev. D, 97, 013007 \(2017\)](#)

Combining x-sec, W-helicity and asymmetry to increase sensitivity to BSM

- * in the EFT framework
- * most recent asymmetries result from ATLAS included
- * very general approach: couplings (real+imaginary) allowed to vary simultaneously

Global constraints

[Phys. Rev. D, 97, 013007 \(2017\)](#)

Combining x-sec, W-helicity and asymmetry to increase sensitivity to BSM

- * in the EFT framework
- * most recent asymmetries result from ATLAS included
- * very general approach: couplings (real+imaginary) allowed to vary simultaneously

$V_L = 1$

$W_{hel} \oplus \sigma_{t,Wt,s}$	g_R	g_L	V_R
Re	[-0.07, 0.08]	[-0.18, 0.20]	[-0.33, 0.41]
Im	[-0.23, 0.23]	[-0.20, 0.19]	[-0.39, 0.36]
$\oplus A_{FB}^{\ell}, A_{FB}^T, A_{FB}^N$	g_R	g_L	V_R
Re	[-0.07, 0.06]	[-0.19, 0.19]	[-0.27, 0.33]
Im	[-0.19, 0.13]	[-0.18, 0.19]	[-0.30, 0.30]

floating V_L

All obs.	g_R	g_L	V_R	V_L
Re	[-0.07, 0.07]	[-0.23, 0.22]	[-0.35, 0.39]	[0.85, 1.08]
Im	[-0.20, 0.15]	[-0.22, 0.23]	[-0.37, 0.39]	—

3-angle analysis

[JHEP 1712 \(2017\) 017](#)

ATLAS
EXPERIMENT

Measurement of triple-differential angular decay rates of single top quarks produced in the t-channel (20.2 fb⁻¹, 8 TeV)

- * 3D angular (θ, θ^*, ϕ^*) decay rate using the helicity formalism
- * relative phases can only be measured with polarised top quarks
- * polarisation (P) can only be measured in single top-quark events

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\theta, \theta^*, \phi^*; P) &= \frac{1}{N} \frac{d^3 N}{d \cos \theta d \Omega^*} = \frac{1}{8\pi} \left\{ \frac{3}{4} |A_{1, \frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 + P \cos \theta) (1 + \cos \theta^*)^2 \right. \\ &+ \frac{3}{4} |A_{-1, -\frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 - P \cos \theta) (1 - \cos \theta^*)^2 \\ &+ \frac{3}{2} \left(|A_{0, \frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 - P \cos \theta) + |A_{0, -\frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 + P \cos \theta) \right) \sin^2 \theta^* \\ &- \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2} P \sin \theta \sin \theta^* (1 + \cos \theta^*) \operatorname{Re} \left[e^{i\phi^*} A_{1, \frac{1}{2}} A_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^* \right] \\ &\left. - \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2} P \sin \theta \sin \theta^* (1 - \cos \theta^*) \operatorname{Re} \left[e^{-i\phi^*} A_{-1, -\frac{1}{2}} A_{0, -\frac{1}{2}}^* \right] \right\} = \end{aligned}$$

W-helicity terms

2-angle analysis

3-angle analysis

$$= \sum_{k=0}^2 \sum_{l=0}^2 \sum_{m=-l}^l a_{k,l,m} M_{k,l}^m(\theta, \theta^*, \phi^*)$$

Finite series of orthonormal
M-functions

3-angle analysis

[JHEP 1712 \(2017\) 017](#)

ATLAS
EXPERIMENT

Detector effects deconvolved from data by measuring differential rates using Fourier techniques (OSDE)

- * The generalised helicity fractions (three independent: f_1, f_1^+, f_0^+) and phases (δ_+, δ_-) + P (nuisance) are determined **simultaneously, including all correlations**
 - ◇ possibility to separate f_0 into two components (+ and -)

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\theta, \theta^*, \phi^*; P) &= \frac{1}{N} \frac{d^3 N}{d \cos \theta d \Omega^*} = \frac{1}{8\pi} \left\{ \frac{3}{4} |A_{1, \frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 + P \cos \theta) (1 + \cos \theta^*)^2 \right. \\ &+ \frac{3}{4} |A_{-1, -\frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 - P \cos \theta) (1 - \cos \theta^*)^2 \\ &+ \frac{3}{2} \left(|A_{0, \frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 - P \cos \theta) + |A_{0, -\frac{1}{2}}|^2 (1 + P \cos \theta) \right) \sin^2 \theta^* \\ &- \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2} P \sin \theta \sin \theta^* (1 + \cos \theta^*) \operatorname{Re} \left[e^{i\phi^*} A_{1, \frac{1}{2}} A_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^* \right] \\ &\left. - \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2} P \sin \theta \sin \theta^* (1 - \cos \theta^*) \operatorname{Re} \left[e^{-i\phi^*} A_{-1, -\frac{1}{2}} A_{0, -\frac{1}{2}}^* \right] \right\} = \end{aligned}$$

W-helicity terms

2-angle analysis

3-angle analysis

$$= \sum_{k=0}^2 \sum_{l=0}^2 \sum_{m=-l}^l a_{k,l,m} M_{k,l}^m(\theta, \theta^*, \phi^*)$$

Finite series of orthonormal
M-functions

3-angle analysis

[JHEP 1712 \(2017\) 017](#)

ATLAS
EXPERIMENT

Helicity fractions & phases determined w/o assumptions on other parameters

- * distributions (profiles and contours) from numerical calculations of the likelihood function
- * interpretation in terms of anomalous couplings V_L , V_R , g_R and g_L
- * overall normalisation V_L set by cross-section measurements

In agreement with SM predictions

3-angle analysis

[JHEP 1712 \(2017\) 017](#)

ATLAS
EXPERIMENT

Limits @95% C.L.:

* $|V_R/V_L| < 0.37$ $|g_L/V_L| < 0.29$

◇ tighter limits from $b \rightarrow s\gamma$ and W helicity with assumptions on other parameters

* $\text{Re}[g_R]/V_L \in [-0.12, 0.17]$ $\text{Im}[g_R]/V_L \in [-0.07, 0.06]$

In agreement with SM predictions

conclusions

Wtb vertex carefully probed during Run I in top-quark production and decay

- * BSM effects on Wtb vertex probed in the EFT framework

Left-handed vector coupling V_L extracted from single top-quark cross-sections

- * most precise combination $|f_{LV}V_{tb}| = \mathbf{0.998 \pm 0.041}$, Run I combination ongoing
- * assumption: $V_R = g_L = g_R = 0$

Wtb anomalous couplings probed in W-helicity measurements

- * assumption: 2 independent F , 4 (real) couplings

Wtb vertex probed through global fit (x-sec+helicity+asymmetries)

- * ATLAS+CMS(+CDF+D0), quite general EFT approach
- * **competitive constraints when $V_L = \mathbf{1}$**

Wtb vertex tested via triple-differential angular decay rates

- * most general approach, ability to separate F_0 into two components (f_0 and f_0^+)
- * **no assumptions** on anomalous couplings

conclusions

All measurements consistent with the SM predictions

- * dominated by systematic uncertainties
- * no sign of new physics BSM so far

Run II data being studied nowadays → even more interesting results soon!

[Phys. Rev. D, 97, 013007 \(2017\)](#)

JHEP 1712 (2017) 017